

Taxonomic Synopsis

1. **Carex** sect. **Paludosae** G.Don in J. C. Loudon, Hort. Brit. 377. 1830.

(1) **Carex acutiformis** Ehrh., Beitr. Naturk. [Ehrhart] 4: 43. 1789.

(2) **Carex amplifolia** Boott in Hook., Fl. Bor.-Amer. 2(11): 228. 1839.

(3) **Carex brownii** Tuck., Enum. Meth. Caric. 21. 1843.

Heterotypic synonyms: *Carex striata* R. Br., Prodr. Fl. Nov. Holland. 243. 1810, non Michx. in 1803; *C. rigens* Boott, Mem. Amer. Acad. Arts ser. 2, 6(2): 419. 1858; *C. transversa* Miq., Ann. Mus. lugd.-batav. II. 148. 1866, non Boott in 1856; *C. nipposinica* Ohwi, Acta Phytotax. et Geobot. 11: 255. 1942.

(4) **Carex benkei** Tak. Shimizu, Acta Phytotax. Geobot. 60(1): 41. 2009.

(5) **Carex confertiflora** Boott, Mem. Amer. Acad. Arts ser. 2, 6(2): 418. 1858.

Homotypic synonym: *Carex olivacea* Boott subsp. *confertiflora* (Boott) T. Koyama, Bot. Mag. (Tokyo) 72: 307. 1959.

Heterotypic synonym: *Carex rhynchophysa* Franch. & Sav., Enum. pl. Japon. II. 155. 1879, non C.A. Mey in 1844.

(6) **Carex dispalata** Boott ex A. Gray, Narr. Exped. China Japan 2: 325. 1856.

Heterotypic synonyms: *Carex acutiformis* Franch., Nouv. Arch. Mus. Paris 3. ser. 10: 83. 1898, non Ehrh in 1789; *C. dispalata* var. *niigatensis* Franch. & Sav., Enum. pl. Japon. II. 580. 1879; *C. subanceps* Boeckeler, Bot. Jahrb. Syst. 5(5): 520. 1884; *C. pollens* C.B. Clarke, J. Linn. Soc., Bot. 36: 305. 1904; *C. dispalata* var. *costata* Kük. in Engler, Pflanzenr. IV, 20(38): 617. 1909.

(7) **Carex honglinii** Y.F. Lu & X.F. Jin, Phytotaxa 372(3): 203. 2018.

(8) **Carex ischnostachya** Steud., Syn. Pl. Glumac. 2(8-9): 222. 1855.

Heterotypic synonym: *Carex ringgoldiana* Boott, Mem. Amer. Acad. Arts ser. 2, 6(2): 419. 1858.

(9) **Carex latisquamea** Kom., Trudy Imp. S.-Peterburgsk. Bot. Sada 18: 447. 1901.

Homotypic synonym: *Carex villosa* Boott var. *latisquamea* (Kom.) Kük. in Engler, Pflanzenr. IV, 20(38): 641. 1909.

Heterotypic synonym: *Carex villosa* Boott in A. Gary, Narr. Exped. China Japan [Perry] 2: 327. 1856.

(10) **Carex nemostachys** Steud., Flora 29: 23. 1846.

Heterotypic synonyms: *Carex excurva* Boott, Ill. Gen. Carex 1: 57. 1858.; *C. kiotensis* H. Lév. & Vaniot, Bull. Acad. Int. Géogr. Bot. 3. sér. 11: 60. 1902, non Franch. & Sav. in 1878.

(11) **Carex obliquicarpa** X.F. Jin, C.Z. Zheng & B.Y. Ding, Ann. Bot. Fenn. 42(3): 223. 2005.

- (12) **Carex olivacea** Boott, Proc. Linn. Soc. London 1(29): 286. 1846.
- (13) **Carex persistens** Ohwi in Mem. Coll. Sci. Kyoto Imp. Univ., Ser. B, Biol. 5: 249. 1930.
- (14) **Carex pseudochinensis** H. Lév. & Vaniot, Bull. Acad. Int. Géogr. Bot. 11: 306. 1902.
- (15) **Carex pseudodispalata** K.T. Fu, Tsinling 1(1): 448. 1976.
- (16) **Carex recurvisaccus** T. Koyama, Jap. J. Bot. 15: 166. 1956.
Homotypic synonym: *Carex olivacea* Boott subsp. *recurvisaccus* (T. Koyama) T. Koyama, Bot. Mag. (Tokyo) 72: 307. 1959.
- (17) **Carex retrofracta** Kük., Repert. Spec. Nov. Regni Veg. Beih. 27: 110. 1929.
Heterotypic synonyms: *Carex purpureotincta* Ohwi, Acta Phytotax. Geobot. 2(3): 159. 1933; *C. haematorrhyncha* Ohwi & T. Koyama, Bull. Natl. Sci. Mus., Tokyo, N.S. 3(38): 21. 1956; *C. purpureotincta* Ohwi var. *sphaerocarpa* Ohwi ex T. Koyama, Jap. J. Bot. 15: 169. 1956.; *C. xiangxiensis* Z. P. Wang, Acta Bot. Yunnan. 11(2): 168. 1989.
- (18) **Carex retrofracta** Kük. subsp. **glabrifolia** Y.F. Lu, H. Wang & X.F. Jin, Phytotaxa 429(2): 144. 2020.
- (19) **Carex sclerocarpa** Franch., Bull. Soc. Philom. Paris, sér. 8, 7: 91. 1895.
- (20) **Carex sinoaristata** Tang et F.T. Wang ex L.K. Dai, Acta Phytotax. Sin. 32(2): 184. 1994.
- (21) **Carex subglabra** (X.F. Jin et C.Z. Zheng) X.F. Jin & Y. F. Lu, Phytotaxa 372(3): 205. 2018.
Basionym: *Carex nemostachys* Steud. var. *subglabra* X.F. Jin et C.Z. Zheng, J. Zhejiang Univ. (Sci. Ed.) 31 (6): 684. 2004.
- (22) **Carex subtumida** (Kük.) Ohwi, Acta Phytotax. Geobot. 1(1): 75. 1932.
Basionym: *Carex ischnostachya* Steud. var. *subtumida* Kük., Repert. Spec. Nov. Regni Veg. 27: 109. 1929.
- (23) **Carex transversa** Boott, Narr. Exped. China Japan 2: 324. 1856.
Homotypic synonym: *Carex brownii* Tuck. var. *transversa* Kük., Engler, Pflanzenr. IV, 20(38): 622. 1909.
- (24) **Carex tumida** Boott, Ill. Gen. Carex 1: 66, t. 181. 1858.
Homotypic synonym: *Carex oedorrhapha* Nelves, Bull. Misc. Inform. Kew 1939: 659. 1939.
- 2. Carex sect. Molliculae** Ohwi, Mem. Coll. Sci. Kyoto Imp. Univ., Ser. B, Biol. 11: 450. 1936.
- (1) **Carex alopecuroides** D. Don ex Tilloch & Taylor in Philos. Mag. J. 62: 455. 1823.
Homotypic synonyms: *Carex emodorum* Spreng. Syst. Veg., ed. 16 3: 818. 1826; *C. japonica* Thunb. var. *alopecuroides* (D. Don) C.B. Clarke in Hook., Fl. Brit. India 6: 737. 1894.

Heterotypic synonyms: *Carex consocialis* Steud., Syn. Pl. Glumac. 2(8-9): 222. 1855; *C. kawakamii* Hayata, J. Coll. Sci. Imp. Univ. Tokyo 30: 385. 1911; *C. pseudojaponica* Hayata, J. Coll. Sci. Imp. Univ. Tokyo 30: 392. 1911, non C.B. Clarke in 1908; *C. hayatana* Honda, Bot. Mag. (Tokyo) 43: 191. 1929; *C. scabrisacca* Ohwi et T. S. Liu, J. Jap. Bot. 12: 655. 1936.

(2) **Carex aphanolepis** Franch. et Sav., Enum. Pl. Jap. 2(1): 152. 1877.

Homotypic synonym: *Carex japonica* Thunb. var. *aphanolepis* (Franch. et Sav.) Kük. in Engler, Pflanzenr. IV, 20(38): 620. 1909.

Heterotypic synonym: *Carex japonica* Thunb. var. *humilis* Franch., Nouv. Arch. Mus. Hist. Nat. sér. 3, 10: 77. 1898.

(3) **Carex doniana** Spreng. Syst. Veg., ed. 16 3: 825. 1826.

Homotypic synonyms: *Carex alopecuroides* D. Don var. *chlorostachya* C.B. Clarke, J. Linn. Soc., Bot. 36: 271. 1903; *C. chlorostachys* D. Don, Philos. Mag. J. 62: 455. 1823, non Steven in 1813; *C. japonica* Boott, Ill. Gen. Carex 2: 88, t. 257. 1860, non Thunb. in 1784; *C. japonica* Thunb. var. *alopecuroides* (D. Don) Kük. in Engler, Pflanzenr. IV, 20(38): 620. 1909.

Heterotypic synonyms: *Carex sasakii* Hayata, J. Coll. Sci. Imp. Univ. Tokyo 30: 395. 1911; *C. zollingeri* Steud., Syn. Pl. Glumac. 2(8-9): 221. 1855.

(4) **Carex huashanica** Tang et F.T. Wang ex L.K. Dai, Acta Phytotax. Sin. 32(2): 186. 1994.

(5) **Carex japonica** Thunb., Fl. Jap. 38. 1784.

Heterotypic synonyms: *Carex albidibasis* T. Koyama, J. Jap. Bot. 30: 136. 1955; *C. japonica* Thunb. var. *gracilis* Franch., Nouv. Arch. Mus. Hist. Nat. sér. 3, 10: 78. 1898; *C. japonica* Boott var. *minor* Boott, Ill. Gen. Carex 2: 88. 1860; *C. doniana* Spreng. var. *minor* (Boott) C.B. Clarke, J. Linn. Soc., Bot. 36: 292. 1903; *C. japoniciformis* Nakai, Rep. Veg. Kamikochi 34 & 42. 1928; *C. motoskei* Miq., Ann. Mus. Bot. Lugduno-Batavi 2: 148. 1865; *C. tokioensis* Boeckeler, Flora 65: 63. 1882; *C. trichostyles* Franch. et Sav., Enum. pl. Jap. II. 581. 1879; *C. japonica* Thunb. var. *trichostyles* Franch. ex H. Lév. & Vaniot, Bull. Acad. Int. Géogr. Bot. 12: 600. 1903.

(6) **Carex liui** T. Koyama & Chuang, Quart. J. Taiwan Mus. 13: 224. 1960.

(7) **Carex mollicula** Boott, Ill. Gen. Carex 4: 192. 1867.

Heterotypic synonyms: *Carex arcuata* Franch., Bull. Soc. Philom. Paris, sér. 7, 10: 106. 1886; *C. macromollicula* Nakai, Rep. Veg. Kamikochi 34 & 41. 1928; *C. mollicula* Boott f. *lutescens* Kük. in Engler, Pflanzenr. IV, 20(38): 622. 1909.

(8) **Carex radicina** Z.P. Wang, J. Nanjing Univ. (Biol.) 1962(2): 53. 1962.

(9) **Carex remotistachya** Y.Y. Zhou & X.F. Jin, Phytotaxa 164(2): 133. 2014.

(10) **Carex submollicula** Tang et F.T. Wang ex L.K. Dai, Acta Phytotax. Sin. 32(2): 186. 1994.

(11) **Carex subtransversa** C.B. Clarke, Philipp. J. Sci., C 2: 108. 1907.

Homotypic synonyms: *Carex japonica* Thunb. subsp. *subtransversa* (C.B. Clarke) T. Koyama, J. Fac. Sci. Univ. Tokyo III 8(4): 213. 1962; *C. alopecuroides* D. Don subsp. *subtransversa* (C.B. Clarke) T. Koyama in H. L. Li et al., Fl. Taiwan 5: 354. 1978.

3. Carex sect. *Alliiformes* Akiyama, Caric. Far East. Reg. As. 143. 1955.

(1) **Carex *alliiformis*** C.B. Clarke, J. Linn. Soc., Bot. 36: 270. 1903.

Heterotypic synonyms: *Carex purpurascens* Kük., J. Coll. Sc. Tokyo 22: 496. 1906; *C. purplevaginalis* Q. S. Wang, J. Wuhan Bot. Res. 5:343. 1987.

(2) **Carex *phaenocarpa*** Franch. in Bull. Soc. philom. Paris 8. ser. 7: 90. 1895.

Homotypic synonym: *Carex japonica* Thunb. var. *phaenocarpa* (Franch.) Kük. in Engler, Pflanzenr. IV, 20(38): 621. 1909.

4. Carex sect. *Harrysmithianae* Y.F. Lu, X.F. Jin & Jim.Mejías, sect. nov.

(1) **Carex *harrysmithii*** Kük., Acta Horti Gothob. 5: 40. 1929.

5. Carex sect. *Agglomeratae* Y.F. Lu, X.F. Jin & Jim.Mejías, sect. nov.

(1) **Carex *agglomerata*** C.B. Clarke, J. Linn. Soc., Bot. 36: 269. 1903.